

ISic0053

I.Sicily inscription 0053

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo

Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3556

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

1. Secundo · XX · her(editatium) ·
2. vil(ico) · summar(um) · Ur ·
3. banae · matri ·
4. Clymene · cog(natae) ·
5. Primigenius · XX · her(editatium) ·
6. se[rvus ---]

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285285
EDR 127506
EDCS 22100048

Bibliography

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- Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 54
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- Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 38 tav.X.16

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